

Training for Forest Technicians, Researchers, and Employees on Fundraising and Communication Topics as Assets for Ecosystem Services Enhancement Projects

Introduction

During the project a specific internal training within the GO focused on fundraising and formation on the transfer of knowledge, in order to increase communication skills of the partnership aimed at disseminating the concept of the environmental service of forests and a collective recognition (also economic) of this service, thanks also to the creation of a carbon credit exchange platform. The main focus was enabling the forest technicians, researchers and employees involved in the project to raise funds and seek financing for forest sustainable management, with a view to attributing a recognised economic value to the storage of carbon (PES - Payment for Environmental Services) in order to improve the communication approach towards interested entrepreneurs, to involve forest and private individuals potentially interested in both the purchase of Sustainability Credits and the PES (Payment for Ecosystem Services) of Ecosystem Services. Beside that, many field initiatives were organized and a series of digital and paper material have been shared in order to disseminate the project results in the territory and raise awareness and interest on sustainable forest management and ecosystem services.

Lessons learned

The sale of sustainability credits and payment for ecosystem services, other than the traditional sale of timber it's an important objective of the OG and can be improved thanks to a good communication strategy and empowering specific communication skills of OG members. During the formation participants have learnt new useful knowledge that will be put in practice adding value to the project and showed interest in the topics addressed showed interest in the meetings, even if were held online due to the Covi-19 emergency.

For further information contact

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Further information

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